

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE AMONG SOCIAL SECURITY SYSTEM CLIENTS IN CALAMBA CITY

Christy C. Mananquil, Marcelina DL. Perez, DBA (CAR)

*School of Graduate Studies, Laguna College of Business and Arts
Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12740199>

ABSTRACT

This study identified the level of effectiveness of digital transformation and customer experiences with digital services among Social Security System clients in Calamba City. A descriptive correlational research method design was used to investigate the relationship between variables. The goal of this study was to understand how the efficacy of digital transformation and the level of customer experience of SSS clients on its digital services related to one another. A total of 215 respondents were selected through purposive sampling, meeting the specific relevant criteria of using the agency's digital services. The study utilized a researcher-made instrument in the form of a survey questionnaire in print and Google Forms, depending on the respondents' preference. A four-point Likert scale, simple mean, and the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient were employed in the study. The results showed that the effectiveness of the digital transformation was at a very high level and was verbally interpreted as highly effective, while the customer experience yielded a very pleasing outcome and was verbally interpreted as very pleasant. Furthermore, the study revealed a significant relationship between digital transformation effectiveness and the level of customer experience in SSS digital services. This suggested that as the level of digital transformation effectiveness increased, the customer experience became more pleasant. Based on the findings, an action plan was proposed to address noted deficiencies and enhance the clientele's experience with SSS digital services.

Keywords: *Digital transformation, Customer experience*

INTRODUCTION

The global corporate economy benefits from digitalization. Businesses and their clientele are constantly evolving as a result of advancements in digital technology and their ongoing expansion. Recent unexpected events that rock the world have a significant impact on numerous businesses and organizations. It open doors to new company ventures, cutting-edge technology, popular corporate concepts, and a shift in consumer viewpoints.

Digitalization is made possible by the increase use of the internet, social media, and technology. Research made by Jaumotte et al. (2023) showed that not only did large companies benefit, but smaller businesses also gained higher returns from digitalization. Due to several contributing factors that led to the adoption and utilization of digital technology, organizations became more agile in responding to shifting market conditions and became ready for digital transformation.

Digital transformation entailed more than just the simple adoption of technology (Ivančić et al., 2019). To properly utilize the potential of digital technologies, firms had to rethink and reinvent current business models and processes. This resulted in significant shifts in how businesses operated, engaged with customers, and delivered value as explained by Mishra et al. (2023).

One of the key drivers is the rapid growth of the country's digital economy. Exito Media Concept (2022) reported that the Philippines had high internet and mobile penetration rates among all of Southeast Asia, creating new opportunities for businesses to grow and interact with clients.

Kemp (2023) cited in a report on Digital 2023 Philippines, stated that there were 85.16 million internet users at the beginning of 2023, with a 73.1 percent internet penetration rate. Additionally, it was reported that there were 84.45 million social media users, representing 72.5 percent of the total population. These headline statistics provided an excellent picture of the "state of digital" in the Philippines.

The Philippines had more exposure to internet usage and social media compared to other countries. However, it was noted that most users did not make use of its educational opportunities or business growth potential. Instead, they predominantly engaged in social media like Facebook, Instagram, and Tiktok. This tendency resulted in gaps in digital skills, as mentioned in an interview with a top official of the Department of Information and Communications Technology (DICT). Meanwhile, other nations made good use of their internet access for various purposes such as government transactions, business creation, employment, education, and learning as claimed by Clapano (2023).

Providing government clients with a great experience is challenging due to the multitude of services to offer, departments to oversee, and procedures to streamline. Moreover, consumers expect a technology-driven, fast, and personalized service similar to what the private sector provided. According to Nelson (2023), citing the IDC Analyst

Brief, governments were the world's largest service providers. However, when it came to customer satisfaction with digital service delivery, the public sector continued to lag behind practically every other sector in terms of efficiency and ease of government process.

As mandated by RA 11032 known as the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018, and the Full Digital Transformation Act of 2020 (Senate Bill No. 1793), which mandated the full digital transformation of all government agencies and other offices, the SSS management responded by improving its processes and services through digitalization. The electronic services of SSS are introduced to the public and a few of its services became available online. These digital transformations are hastened during the COVID-19 pandemic when a zero-contact policy was implemented, facilitating ease of procedures. Some of the advantages include improved efficiency in service delivery, such as streamlining of business processes, accessibility of products and services, global awareness, and transparency in processes and procedures. Some services, such as salary loan applications, SS number applications, and sickness and maternity benefits applications become mandatory to file through the SSS web portal.

Due to the increasing number of SSS members with about 42.56 million members, 32.27 being employed members and the remaining consisting of self-employed individuals, voluntary contributors, and Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs), and with an SSS workforce of around 6,300 (SSS Facts & Figures, August 2023), satisfying the needs of each individual member, whether through manual or digital platforms, posed a significant challenge for the agency.

With the given concept, this study identifies if digital government services can enhance or elevate the expectations for positive customer experiences or create negative experiences that could lead to customer complaints. This research also seek to identify any gaps in digital platforms that may have an impact on the agency's level of service. Additionally, it aims to determine whether the digital transformation increase service efficiency or demoralize clients who find it difficult to adjust to new procedures. Furthermore, the study aims to ascertain what measures the company can have developed to minimize customer complaints and entice more clients to use the online platform rather than the manual procedure.

Summary of Related Literature

The research studies and literature provided a complex and multidimensional picture of digital transformation and customer experience. Thus, this research attempted to create a more sophisticated understanding of the connections between digital transformation and customer experience by integrating the existing literature.

Fitzgerald et al. (2014, as cited in Kraus et al., 2021), Zaoui and Souissi (2020), Fang (2002, as cited in Mohsen & Magdi, 2022), and Verhoef et al. (2021), emphasized

the need for a clear strategy, use of emerging technologies, customer experience, as well as benefits and challenges involved.

Meanwhile, Van Veldhoven and Vantienen (2022), RTG Solutions Group (2023), Borges et al. (2020), Awadhi et al. (2021), and Collins (2023), highlighted the importance of embracing digital transformation to satisfy customers, deliver tailored experiences, and raise customer satisfaction levels.

Whereas, Albukhitan (2020), Wang et al. (2020, as cited in Mohsen & Magdi, 2022), Matt et al. (2015, as cited in Hanelt et al., 2021), and Tekic and Koroteev (2019) all recognized that enterprises needed a clearly defined digital transformation strategy to effectively integrate digital transitions, promote innovation, and foresee and respond to changes.

On the other hand, Correani et al. (2020), Pearce (2020), Gokalp and Martinez (2021), Mikalef and Parmiggiani (2022), Xiao et al. (2022), Mergel et al. (2019), and Van Veldhoven and Vanthienen (2022) collectively stressed the transformative impact of technology on value creation, customer-centricity, and the challenges faced by businesses in adapting to new technologies.

Accordingly, Mishra et al. (2023), Yu et al. (2022), and Tian et al. (2023) all claimed how important it was to take into account the organizational context, modify internal procedures, include digital services, and acknowledge the broader scope and effects of digital transformation on operations.

Likewise, Ivančić et al. (2019), Butt et al. (2024), Brunetti et al. (2020), Udovita (2022), and Deep (2023) emphasized the essential of creating a digital culture, viewing digital transformation as an ongoing process, and utilizing culture as a mechanism to drive the adoption of digital technology.

Meanwhile, Alvarenga et al. (2020), Xiao et al. (2022), Access Partnership (2023), Reganit (2023), and Carlos (2023) all acknowledged the necessity of public digital literacy and central government support in achieving successful digitalization results while highlighting technological preparedness, organizational efficiency, public service delivery, and public expectations.

Together, Oracle (2023), McKinsey and Company (2022), Roy et al. (2022), Bascur and Rusu (2022), Becker and Jaakkola (2021), and Waqas et al. (2021) stressed the significance of providing superior customer experiences and value; emotional engagement; the connection between customer experience and customer commitment.

Meanwhile, Heller et al. (2021), Watts (2020) and Hadid et al. (2022) collectively acknowledged that utilizing visual components and making sure the user experience was smooth and aesthetically pleasing were key to giving digital services a sense of tangibility.

Conversely, Ranchordas (2021), Khan (2023), and Mathis (2021) all underlined the significance of empathy in fostering understanding, support, and positive outcomes across various contexts.

On one hand, Gupta (2024), TAFF Inc. (2021), Susanto et al. (2023), and Khatoon et al. (2020) collectively emphasized the necessity of businesses to adapt to digital platforms to satisfy consumers' preferences for reliable and safe online services, convenience, and security, as well as customer confidence in internet services and privacy protection.

On the other hand, TAFF Inc. (2021), Chen et al. (2021), and Korach (2023) highlighted the relevance of responsiveness in digital services as it enhanced client contentment, trust, and loyalty were enhanced by prompt and effective replies, individualized experiences, and problem-solving.

Consequently, Watts (2020), Janota (2023), and Wipro (2023) explained that assurance was essential in the digital world as it encompassed compliance, security, and trustworthiness to create successful digital platforms.

Moreover, Moore (2023), RTG Solutions Group (2023), Lund (2023), Masoud and Basahel (2023), and Elev8tek (2024) emphasized that prioritizing customer-centric digital transformation, leveraging advanced technologies and real-time data, enabled businesses to deliver highly tailored, effective, and fulfilling experiences that met evolving needs.

In summary, the authors collectively recognized the importance and challenges of digital transformation based on five business dimensions. They also acknowledged the significance of service quality theory in understanding customer experience. Furthermore, they highlighted the vital role that digital transformation plays in enhancing customer experience.

After conducting a comprehensive review of the literature on digital transformation, it was observed that the majority of studies focused on the adoption of technology and its impact on customer experience in businesses. However, few studies investigated digital transformation based on the core dimensions of business and its relationship with customer experience in government digital services. Some existing literature and body of knowledge was lacking or unclear, thus, some potential conceptual gaps were tried to address. Therefore, this study sought to examine and integrate the implications of emerging digital technologies and customer behavior and experiences on government digital services that had not been effectively addressed in existing literature.

Furthermore, no study had been conducted in Calamba City regarding digital transformation and its effect on customer experience. Therefore, this study aimed to bridge this spatial gap and contribute to the expansion of understanding of digital transformation and customer experience within government agencies.

Research Questions

This study focused on the relationship between digital transformation and customer experience as assessed by clients of Social Security System in Calamba City. Specifically, this study aims to address the following questions:

1. What is the level of digital transformation effectiveness in SSS as assessed by clients in terms of:
 - 1.1 customer,
 - 1.2 strategy,
 - 1.3 technology,
 - 1.4 operations, and
 - 1.5 organization and culture?
 2. What is the level of customer experience on digital services among SSS clients in terms of:
 - 2.1 tangibility,
 - 2.2 empathy,
 - 2.3 reliability,
 - 2.4 responsiveness, and
 - 2.5 assurance?
 3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of digital transformation effectiveness and the level of customer experience in SSS digital services?
 4. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?
-

METHODOLOGY

The design used in this study was descriptive correlational design which aimed to examine how variables relate to one another and explain their features without suggesting a cause. According to Creswell (2012, as cited by Sharma, 2023), it was a non-experimental quantitative design in which the researcher used correlational statistics to assess and characterize the degree of relationship between variables or sets of scores. This design aimed to provide significant insights into associations between variables through data collection and analysis. Descriptive correlational design contributed to the body of knowledge and served as a baseline for future research and exploration.

Locale

The study involved the participation of SSS clients who transacted at the SSS Calamba Branch and had used the SSS online platform. This locale was chosen where the researcher was an employee who had easy access to any needed information and had actual involvement in the phenomenon.

Population and Sampling

This study used purposive sampling, wherein participants who were chosen possessed the desired experiences or met the specific characteristics relevant to the

topic. GPower application was utilized in computing the actual sample based on daily walk-in clients. The estimated sample size from an average 1000 population of daily walk-in clients was approximately 215 respondents with a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error.

Instrument

A survey questionnaire was used as the main instrument to obtain the necessary data needed for the study. Researcher-made questionnaires with tailored questions aligned with the study were used. The survey questionnaire for the respondents was composed of three parts. The first part consisted of the profile of the clients; the second part assessed the effectiveness of digital information perceived by clients and third part focused on the client’s customer experience with SSS digital services.

The participants of the study answered part 2 and 3 using a 4-point Likert scale survey. The following components make up the scaling:

Scale for the Level of Effectiveness of Digital Transformation

Range	Scale	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
3.25 – 4.00	4	Strongly Agree	Highly Effective
2.50 – 3.24	3	Agree	Effective
1.75 – 2.49	2	Disagree	Slightly Effective
1.00 – 1.74	1	Strongly Disagree	Not Effective

Scale for the Level of Customer Experience on Digital Services

Range	Scale	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
3.25 – 4.00	4	Strongly Agree	Very Pleasant
2.50 – 3.24	3	Agree	Pleasant
1.75 – 2.49	2	Disagree	Slightly Pleasant
1.00 – 1.74	1	Strongly Disagree	Unpleasant

Validation of Instrument

The research-made survey instrument was presented to an adviser for review, and necessary modifications were made before submitting it for approval by the Dean. Afterward, the instrument was sent to 5 expert validators: the Research Director, Statistician, MBA Professor, and two of the highest-ranking Executive Officers of the company. The Content Validity Index (CVI) was then calculated based on the ratings obtained from a panel of experts who evaluated each question or item in the measurement instrument. The result of CVI was 1, which was higher than 0.99, indicating excellent content validity and deemed acceptable.

After the validation of instruments, they were sent out to 15 participants for pilot testing. The survey results were collected and subjected to Alpha Cronbach analysis for reliability testing. Cronbach's alpha results were .961 for digital transformation and .969 for customer experience, which indicated excellent internal consistency reliability. The results were deemed acceptable by the statistician who performed the analysis. With the instrument now ready, it could be distributed to the intended respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

The letter had been presented to the branch manager before the study to obtain permission to administer a survey questionnaire to walk-in members who transacted at the Calamba Branch. Upon approval, the researcher determined the participants using purposive sampling wherein the participants were chosen based on the characteristic that they had already used the online services of SSS in their transactions. The researcher handed out the printed survey questionnaires or used Google Forms, depending on the applicable method, to the respondents. After providing the respondents with sufficient time to answer the questionnaire, the responses were collected and organized. After all the responses had been gathered, a statistician assisted the researcher in the process of tabulating and analyzing the data. The survey was conducted for five days until the desired number of participants had been reached and completed.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

The following statistical treatment was utilized during the research study:

1. The level of effectiveness of the digital transformation and the level of customer experience with SSS digital services were measured using a mean and a four-point Likert scale.
2. The significant relationship between the level of digital transformation effectiveness and the level of customer experience in SSS digital services was evaluated using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient.

Scope and Delimitation

This quantitative descriptive correlational study focused on the effectiveness of digital transformation in SSS through mandatory digital services rendered by the company and addressed its digital capability in terms of five core dimensions: customers, strategy, technology, operations, and organization and culture. The digital platform studied was anchored on the SSS website and SSS mobile app with services available such as SS number application, registration to the SSS portal, benefit claim application, loan application, disbursement account enrollment, payment reference number generation, updated contact information, access to member's records and others. Furthermore, the research concentrated on the application of service quality to assess customer experience through five service dimensions namely tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

Since this study was limited to members or clients who engaged in online transactions using the SSS website or SSS mobile app, respondents came from the Calamba Branch E-Center facility, a self-service electronic center with available computers used by clients for their online transactions with minimal assistance or intervention from SSS employees. Other respondents interviewed were walk-in clients who had previously or continuously used the SSS online services for mandatory online transactions. The total number of respondents was 215, comprising clients of the SSS Calamba Branch.

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Level of Digital Transformation Effectiveness in SSS as assessed by Clients in terms of Customer

Indicators in terms of Customer	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The agency, digital transformation efforts have improved my experience and met my needs and expectations as a customer.	3.65	HE	1
2. My involvement and interactions on the agency's digital platforms have increased.	3.55	HE	4
3. I am pleased with the online services provided by the agency.	3.64	HE	2
4. The agency promptly addresses my feedback and resolves issues through digital channel.	3.43	E	6
5. The agency enhances its digital services to match my changing needs.	3.53	HE	5
6. My overall satisfaction and loyalty as a customer increased due agency's digital transformation.	3.59	HE	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.57	HE	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Highly Effective (HE)	1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Effective (SE)		
2.50 – 3.24 Effective (E)	1.00 – 1.74 Not Effective (NE)		

Table 1.2
Level of Digital Transformation Effectiveness in SSS as assessed by Clients in terms of Strategy

Indicators in terms of Strategy	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The agency is effectively implementing its roadmap to digitalization.	3.56	HE	3
2. The agency has communicated its digital strategy to its stakeholders.	3.54	HE	4
3. The agency's digital strategy aims to deliver continuous improvements to its services and add value to customers.	3.64	HE	1
4. The agency's digital transformation efforts are aligned with industry standards and adopt the latest technological advancements.	3.58	HE	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.58	HE	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Highly Effective (HE)	1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Effective (SE)		
2.50 – 3.24 Effective (E)	1.00 – 1.74 Not Effective (NE)		

Table 1.3

Level of Digital Transformation Effectiveness in SSS as assessed by Clients in terms of Technology

Indicators in terms of Technology	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The agency keeps up with emerging technologies and adapts them to digital transformation initiatives.	3.65	HE	1
2. I am very satisfied with the use and function of the agency's digital tools and platforms.	3.64	HE	2.5
3. I am quite confident in the agency's ability to ensure the security of its digital systems and protect the privacy of my data.	3.64	HE	2.5
4. I have not encountered any challenges or difficulties in using new digital technologies implemented by the agency.	3.13	E	6
5. I am pleased with the speed and performance of the agency's digital systems and applications.	3.27	HE	5
6. The agency's digital services work smoothly and are compatible with any existing operating systems and devices.	3.38	HE	4
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.45	HE	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Highly Effective (HE)	1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Effective (SE)		
2.50 – 3.24 Effective (E)	1.00 – 1.74 Not Effective (NE)		

Table 1.4

Level of Digital Transformation Effectiveness in SSS as assessed by Clients in terms of Operations

Indicators in terms of Operations	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The agency's digital transformation has significantly streamlined its processes and improved the efficiency of their transactions.	3.57	HE	1
2. Digital technologies and automation have enhanced the agency's ability to deliver products or services in a timely manner.	3.51	HE	3
3. Digital transformation has resulted in a improved communication and collaboration with customer.	3.55	HE	2
4. I believe the agency's digital operations are quite dependable, with minimal instances of downtime or disruptions.	3.40	HE	4
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.51	HE	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Highly Effective (HE)	1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Effective (SE)		
2.50 – 3.24 Effective (E)	1.00 – 1.74 Not Effective (NE)		

Table 1.5

Level of Digital Transformation Effectiveness in SSS as assessed by Clients in terms of Organization and Culture

Indicators in terms of Organization and Culture	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The agency shows an immediate response in adapting digital transformation.	3.58	HE	5
2. I have observed major changes in the processes or transactions as a result of agency's digital transformation.	3.62	HE	4
3. The staffs are equipped with abilities and knowledge required to take part in digital transformation process.	3.80	HE	1
4. The agency has established effective communication channels to ensure that customers are well- informed and actively involved in digital transformation initiatives.	3.65	HE	3
5. The agency continues to develop and strengthens its digital processes and capabilities.	3.73	HE	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.67	HE	

Table 2.1

Level of Customer Experience on Digital Services among SSS Clients in terms of Tangibility

Indicators in terms of Tangibility	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The design of digital platforms (SSS website and mobile app) is visually appealing and user-friendly.	3.57	VP	3
2. The digital service of the agency provides relevant and up-to-date information.	3.70	VP	1
3. It is easy to access and find needed information or services on the digital platforms of the agency.	3.55	VP	4
4. The digital service works on a variety of devices and platforms.	3.45	VP	5
5. The agency's digital profile reflects a modern and respectable image.	3.67	VP	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.59	VP	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Very Pleasant (VP) 1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Pleasant (SP)
 2.50 – 3.24 Pleasant (P) 1.00 – 1.74 Unpleasant (U)

Table 2.2

Level of Customer Experience on Digital Services among SSS Clients in terms of Empathy

Indicators in terms of Empathy	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The digital platforms cater to my individual needs and preferences.	3.70	VP	1
2. The digital service provides me with personalized experience and recommendations.	3.66	VP	2
3. I receive prompt and helpful customer support in using digital channels.	3.54	VP	4
4. I find the agency's availability and accessibility through diverse channels for support and assistance to be fulfilling.	3.55	VP	3
5. The agency understands and empathizes with the difficulties I encounter in adopting and utilizing digital tools.	3.53	VP	5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.60	VP	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Very Pleasant (VP) 1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Pleasant (SP)
 2.50 – 3.24 Pleasant (P) 1.00 – 1.74 Unpleasant (U)

Table 2.3*Level of Customer Experience on Digital Services among SSS Clients in terms of Reliability*

Indicators in terms of Reliability	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The digital platforms are available and accessible when I need it.	3.46	VP	4
2. The digital service performs accurately without any errors or interruption.	3.26	VP	5
3. I am satisfied that the digital services are delivered with consistent speed and responsiveness.	3.47	VP	3
4. I am confident that the digital service ensures data security and privacy.	3.63	VP	1
5. The digital system and processes of the agency deliver precise and current information.	3.62	VP	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.49	VP	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Very Pleasant (VP) 1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Pleasant (SP)
2.50 – 3.24 Pleasant (P) 1.00 – 1.74 Unpleasant (U)

Table 2.4*Level of Customer Experience on Digital Services among SSS Clients in terms of Responsiveness*

Indicators in terms of Responsiveness	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The digital service promptly acknowledges my queries or complaints.	3.43	VP	5
2. The digital platforms provide timely updates and notifications regarding my transactions.	3.62	VP	2
3. The agency takes proper measure to resolve my concerns regarding digital services.	3.59	VP	3
4. The agency seeks feedback from its clients to improve its digital services.	3.63	VP	1
5. My feedback and suggestions regarding digital transformation efforts are highly valued and prioritized by the agency.	3.47	VP	4
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.55	VP	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Very Pleasant (VP) 1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Pleasant (SP)
2.50 – 3.24 Pleasant (P) 1.00 – 1.74 Unpleasant (U)

Table 2.5*Level of Customer Experience on Digital Services among SSS Clients in terms of Assurance*

Indicators in terms of Assurance	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The digital service provides transparent and accurate information about its products and services.	3.63	VP	4
2. The digital service has a user-friendly platform that is easy to navigate.	3.52	VP	5
3. The staff is competent in providing adequate knowledge and assistance regarding my digital transactions.	3.77	VP	1
4. I feel confident in the integrity and trustworthiness of the digital services of the agency.	3.71	VP	3
5. I believe my personal information is secure when using the agency's digital platforms and services.	3.74	VP	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.68	VP	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Very Pleasant (VP) 1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Pleasant (SP)
2.50 – 3.24 Pleasant (P) 1.00 – 1.74 Unpleasant (U)

Table 3

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Digital Transformation Effectiveness and the Level of Customer Experience in SSS Digital Services

Digital Transformation Effectiveness	Customer Experience	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Customer	Tangibility	.736**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Empathy	.636**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Reliability	.713**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Responsiveness	.668**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Assurance	.642**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
Strategy	Tangibility	.744**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Empathy	.679**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Reliability	.748**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Responsiveness	.710**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Assurance	.751**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
Technology	Tangibility	.800**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Empathy	.697**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Reliability	.863**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Responsiveness	.718**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Assurance	.705**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
Operations	Tangibility	.804**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Empathy	.721**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Reliability	.795**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Responsiveness	.708**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Assurance	.707**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
Organization and Culture	Tangibility	.741**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Empathy	.758**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Reliability	.643**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Responsiveness	.714**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Assurance	.771**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

Table 4
Proposed Action Plan

AREAS OF CONCERN	GOALS/ OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	TIME FRAME	PERSONS INVOLVED	SOURCE OF FUND	SUCCESS INDICATORS
Technology	To address difficulties in using new technologies	1. Make the new technologies' designs and user interfaces more user-friendly, intuitive, and in line with consumer expectations	6 months	IT Department	Budget Dept	1. Increase user satisfaction scores by at least 20%.
		2. Provide thorough and easy-to-read FAQs, tutorials, and user guides that include detailed instructions and troubleshooting data.	6 months	Member Education Department		2. Release user guides for every new technology.
		3. Plan webinars, workshops, and training sessions to instruct clients on how to use the new technology successfully and efficiently.	ongoing	Learning and Development Department		3. Educate at least 80% of users on the main features and capabilities.
		4. Collect client feedback on their experience with new technology and utilize it to make continuous improvements.	ongoing	Quality Management Department		4. Obtain favorable response from at least 90% of clients in post-implementation surveys.

AREAS OF CONCERN	GOALS/ OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	TIME FRAME	PERSONS INVOLVED	SOURCE OF FUND	SUCCESS INDICATORS
Reliability	To minimize system downtime and disruptions	1. Invest in a dependable and scalable infrastructure that can handle increased user traffic, eliminate any interruptions, and reduce downtime.	1 year	IT Department	Budget Dept	1. At least 99.9% uptime should be attained for digital services.
		2. Implement redundancy and failover techniques to ensure digital service continuity in the case of system errors or disruptions.	6 months	IT Department		2. Install redundancy and failover systems successfully, with 0-2% critical failures.
		3. Create a routine maintenance schedule to perform system updates, patches, and fixes to address vulnerabilities and reduce downtime proactively.	6 months	Learning and Development Department		3. Establish a regular maintenance schedule with a maximum of 2% of service interruptions.
		4. Develop an incident response plan to handle disruptions effectively, minimize downtime, and ensure timely recovery of digital services	ongoing	Quality Management Department		4. Educate at least 80% of users on the main features and capabilities

DISCUSSION

Table 1.1

Level of Digital Transformation Effectiveness in SSS as assessed by Clients in terms of Customer

Customer was **Highly Effective (3.57)** as to the level of digital transformation effectiveness in SSS as assessed by clients. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Highly Effective. Furthermore, the indicator “The agency’s digital transformation efforts have improved my experience and met my needs and expectations as a customer” had the highest computed mean of **3.65** while the indicator “The agency promptly addresses my feedback and resolves issues through digital means.” had the lowest computed mean of **3.43**.

This means that digital transformation is highly effective in SSS in terms of Customer as assessed by the clients. The clients affirm that their experience with SSS' digital transformation has improved, their expectations have been satisfied, and they are happy with their interaction and involvement in SSS' online services. This indicates that SSS offers their clients the necessary digital services to a significant extent.

The aforementioned findings were associated with research conducted by Borges et al. (2020) on digital transformation in banks. According to World Retail Banking Report 2016, an enhanced banking experience was observed in 85% of the nation. He further mentioned that reviews of digital services were largely positive. Customers could see more details about their account, operate on their own, and experience less waiting time in the branch.

Additionally, Awadhi et al. (2021) stated that providing individualized services and digitally empowering experiences boosted customer satisfaction to appeal to a younger and more technologically savvy clientele.

Furthermore, as mentioned by Collins (2023), the implementation of digitalization initiatives, including mobile applications, engagement through social media platforms, and the utilization of artificial intelligence technologies, was shown to have a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty. This was primarily attributed to the provision of personalized, convenient, and seamless interactions that span the entirety of the customer journey.

Table 1.2

Level of Digital Transformation Effectiveness in SSS as assessed by Clients in terms of Strategy

The strategy was **Highly Effective (3.58)** as to the level of digital transformation effectiveness in SSS as assessed by clients. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Highly Effective. Furthermore, the indicator “The agency’s digital strategy aims to deliver continuous improvements on its services and added value to customers” had the highest

computed mean of **3.64** while the indicator “The agency has clearly communicated its digital strategy to its stakeholders” had the lowest computed mean of **3.54**.

This means that digital transformation is highly effective in SSS in terms of Strategy as assessed by the clients. In essence, the agency keeps enhancing its digital goods and services by utilizing technology advancements, understanding consumer needs, and aligning them with the company's objective of providing a superior customer experience. The agency can also concentrate on making efforts to effectively communicate its digitalization goals or road map to clients who would be impacted by this change.

Relative to the strategy dimension of digital transformation, Albukhitan (2020) stated that organizations should have prioritized the establishment of their objectives and vision for Digital Transformation. This involved clearly defining what a successful transformation looked like and understanding its broader implications for their business and customers, particularly in terms of customer experience and engagement.

In addition, Matt et al.(2015, as cited in Hanelt et al.,2021) mentioned that creating a digital transformation strategy that functioned as a central concept for integrating the coordination, prioritizing, and implementation of digital transformations inside a firm was essential for coordinating this integration during the digital transformation process.

Hanelt et al. (2021) also believed that creating a digital business strategy, digital acceleration, and digital mobilization all contribute to the organization's ability to move toward digital efficiency.

Table 1.3 **Level of Digital Transformation Effectiveness in SSS as assessed by Clients in terms of Technology**

Technology was **Highly Effective (3.45)** as to the level of digital transformation effectiveness in SSS as assessed by clients. Furthermore, the indicator “The agency keeps up with emerging technologies and adapts them into digital transformation initiatives” had the highest computed mean of **3.65** verbally interpreted as Highly Effective, meanwhile the indicator “I have not encountered any challenges or difficulties in using new digital technologies implemented by the agency” had the lowest computed mean of **3.13** verbally interpreted as Effective.

This means that digital transformation is highly effective in SSS in terms of Technology as assessed by the clients. This suggests that clients are fully satisfied with the emerging technologies provided by the agency, delivering seamless, compatible, and high-performing digital services. The clients are confident when using the digital tools knowing that their data are safe and secure.

In support of the statement above, Xiao et al. (2022) revealed that technology preparedness was the most critical factor in promoting digital transformation in local governments. Based on this fact, government agencies should have fully utilized digital

technology to enable digital transformation. Governments could have improved organizational efficiency using digital technology, which could have led to a shift toward digital transformation.

Besides, Mergel et al.(2019) cited that adopted from the private sector, the phrase "digital transformation" referred primarily to the necessity of utilizing new technology to maintain competitiveness in the Internet age, where goods and services were provided through both online and offline channels.

Also, Van Veldhoven and Vanthienen (2022) claimed that adopting the newest technologies encouraged efficiency gains and lower costs. Digital technology has emerged as the primary force behind corporate process, communication, product and service, and business model advances in recent years.

Table 1.4
Level of Digital Transformation Effectiveness in SSS as assessed by Clients in terms of Operations

Operations was **Highly Effective (3.51)** as to the level of digital transformation effectiveness in SSS as assessed by clients. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Highly Effective. Furthermore, the indicator “The agency’s digital transformation has significantly streamlined its processes and improved the efficiency of their transactions” had the highest computed mean of **3.57** while the indicator “I believe the agency’s digital operations are quite dependable, with minimal instances of downtime or disruptions” had the lowest computed mean of **3.40**.

This means that digital transformation is highly effective in SSS in terms of Operations as assessed by the clients. The agency enables streamlining of its processes and increases the efficiency of transactions through an automated digital system as well as communication and collaboration with its clients. Nonetheless, the agency can take into account the dependability of its digital operations, particularly in terms of downtime or disruption.

The results were related to the study of Yu et al. (2022) wherein they cited that the organization's operational performance could be enhanced by digital transformation. Enterprises could have achieved safe, intelligent, and sustainable operations with the support of digital transformation, which incorporated sustainable development into the enterprise value chain.

Likewise, Tian et al. (2023) claimed that a company's operational efficiency was greatly enhanced by digital transformation approaches. Therefore, introducing and putting into practice digital methods could have enhanced a company's operations. In addition, they believed that the adoption and implementation of digital technology, as well as the influence of digital transformation on operational efficiency, increased given the growing significance of digital transformation in operations improvement.

Table 1.5

Level of Digital Transformation Effectiveness in SSS as assessed by Clients in terms of Organization and Culture

Organization and Culture was **Highly Effective (3.67)** as to the level of digital transformation effectiveness in SSS as assessed by clients. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Highly Effective. Furthermore, the indicator “The staff are equipped with abilities and knowledge required to take part in digital transformation process” had the highest computed mean of 3.80 while the indicator “The agency shows an immediate response in adapting digital transformation” had the lowest computed mean of **3.58**.

This means that digital transformation is highly effective in SSS in terms of Organization and Culture as assessed by the clients. Employees are empowered with skills and knowledge to embrace the digital transformation process. The agency continues to develop and strengthen its digital capabilities, ensuring that customers are well informed of this major change.

Relative to the study of Xiao et al. (2022), they demonstrated that local governments' digital transformation was positively impacted by organizational effectiveness. The modern government's objective was to increase organizational efficiency. Traditional governments often had poor office efficiency, excessive administrative expenditures, and a lack of information flow across departments. These issues eroded public confidence and undermined the legitimacy of the government.

Brunetti et al. (2020) also stated that essentially, digital culture spoke to the necessity of developing an optimistic and open mindset regarding upcoming technological difficulties. To motivate, involve, and lessen information asymmetry about the digitalization process, it was important to be able to overcome resistance to digitalization through transparency-oriented behavior.

In addition, Udovita (2022) stated that the company had to alter or adapt the organization's structure, incentives, and culture and to begin with, the organizational structure had to be aligned with the transformation process as part of the organization function.

Table 2.1

Level of Customer Experience on Digital Services among SSS Clients in terms of Tangibility

Tangibility was as **Very Pleasant (3.59)** as to the level of customer experience on digital services among SSS clients. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Pleasant. Furthermore, the indicator “The digital service of the agency provides relevant and up-to-date information” had the highest computed mean of **3.70** while the indicator “The digital service works on a variety of devices and platforms” had the lowest computed mean of **3.45**.

This means that the customer experience of digital services among SSS clients is very pleasant in terms of Tangibility. Through elements such as up-to-date information, visually appealing and user-friendly platforms, accessibility, reliable performance, customization options, and modern digital profiles, businesses created a tangible sense of value and meaningful outcomes for users. By focusing on these aspects, businesses can enhance the overall customer experience and build strong relationships with their digital service offerings.

In the study presented by Heller et al. (2021), the digital automation of physical services was driven by the emergence of augmented reality technology, which uses wearable and mobile computers to overlay digital material and change customers' perceptions of a physical service setting. Specifically, it claimed to have attained tangibility even in digitally provided service encounters. For this reason, automated services needed to have a strong visual presence.

Table 2.2
Level of Customer Experience on Digital Services among SSS Clients in terms of Empathy

Empathy was **Very Pleasant (3.60)** as to the level of customer experience on digital services among SSS clients. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Pleasant. Furthermore, the indicator “The digital platforms cater to my individual needs and preferences” had the highest computed mean of **3.70** while the indicator “The agency understands and empathizes with the difficulties I encounter in adopting and utilizing digital tools” had the lowest computed mean of **3.53**.

This means that the customer experience of digital services among SSS clients is very pleasant in terms of Empathy. The clients strongly agree that by using digital services, their individual needs and preferences are being catered to, personalized interactions are being achieved, and responsive customer support is being provided. This means that the agency incorporates empathy into the design and delivery of digital services thus, enhancing user engagement and leading to a more positive customer experience.

As mentioned in the study of Ranchordas (2021), it had been especially crucial for public employees to show empathy for vulnerable citizens, such as the elderly, the disabled, and minorities who were underrepresented. Those who were more susceptible could have been unable to utilize internet platforms, making it impossible for them to exercise their rights. This idea offered ways to make digital government more relatable and enhance comprehension to enable automated decision-making of the requirements of the people. Empathy in administration recognized that citizens had distinct needs and skill sets, and this required redesigned as well as support in utilizing pre-filled application forms, official websites, and algorithms.

Additionally, Khan (2023) mentioned that people could express their ideas, discuss their experiences, and look for support on platforms provided by the digital world.

Giving people in need emotional support required empathy, which was essential. We had a tremendous impact on someone's well-being when we responded with empathy and compassion in our online encounters. A supportive remark, an online hug, or a nice phrase could lift people's spirits and let them know they were not alone. Empathy allowed us to build a virtual support system that cuts across geographical boundaries and supports resilience and mental health in the digital sphere.

Table 2.3
Level of Customer Experience on Digital Services among SSS Clients in terms of Reliability

Reliability was **Very Pleasant (3.49)** as to the level of customer experience on digital services among SSS clients. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Pleasant. Furthermore, the indicator “I am confident that the digital service ensures data security and privacy” had the highest computed mean of **3.63** while the indicator “The digital service performs accurately without any errors or interruption” had the lowest computed mean of **3.26**.

This means that the customer experience of digital services among SSS clients is very pleasant in terms of Reliability. The majority of respondents express their confidence in the security and privacy of their data and have a strong preference for the agency’s digital services to consistently deliver precise information and functionality, availability, and accessibility, with minimal technical issues or disruption.

Relative thereto, a study conducted by Gupta (2024) revealed that customer reliability had increased as digital technology was adopted more widely. Digitalization in banking offers advantages such as increased consumer comfort, flexibility, and reach. Customers could access their account information and complete transactions from any location and at any time, thanks to the advancements of internet and smartphone banking. Customers did not need to visit bank branches, saving them time and effort physically.

In addition, TAFF Inc. (2021) stated that globally, consumers had already shifted to digital platforms, and businesses had to adapt to avoid losing out on business. Consumers would rather have purchased goods or services online through a reliable and safe digital platform.

Table 2.4
Level of Customer Experience on Digital Services among SSS Clients in terms of Responsiveness

Responsiveness was **Very Pleasant (3.55)** as to the level of customer experience on digital services among SSS clients. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Pleasant. Furthermore, the indicator “The agency seeks feedback from its client to improve its digital services” had the highest computed mean of **3.63** while the indicator

“The digital service promptly acknowledges my queries or complaints” had the lowest computed mean of **3.43**.

This means that the customer experience of digital services among SSS clients is very pleasant in terms of Responsiveness. It shows that there is a strong preference for customers’ feedback on the improvement of the the agency’s digital services. Customers value timely updates or notifications to their concerns and expect prompt and efficient responses to their queries or concerns.

Moreover, in the study conducted by Chen et al. (2021), they found that customers perceived retail organizations that employed chatbots as innovative, and with good usability scores offer a personalized experience, solve problems for customers, and make them feel comfortable and respected. Additionally, clients could obtain additional information from the chatbots and benefit from it with no effort thanks to its responsiveness, which had strong beneficial effects on the intrinsic values of the customer experience. Customers were happy when they felt appreciated and comfortable, received personalized conversations, and had their concerns resolved.

Table 2.5
Level of Customer Experience on Digital Services among SSS Clients in terms of Assurance

Assurance was **Very Pleasant (3.68)** as to the level of customer experience on digital services among SSS clients. All indicators were verbally interpreted as Very Pleasant. Furthermore, the indicator “The staff is competent in providing adequate knowledge and assistance regarding my digital transactions” had the highest computed mean of **3.77** while the indicator “The digital service has a user-friendly platform that is easy to navigate” had the lowest computed mean of **3.52**.

This means that customer experience on digital services among SSS clients is very pleasant in terms of Assurance. Clients feel assured when the staff of the agency provides them the adequate knowledge and assistance on their digital transactions. They highly value a sense of trust in the security of their data and the importance of clear and accurate information.

Watts (2020) explained that one of the basic components required to build a successful digital platform was its trustworthiness and security (clear terms and conditions, privacy protection, and assurances about intellectual property and data ownership are required). Crafting an effective digital platform that offered a smooth user experience, reliable transaction processing and strong safeguard against harmful elements was an intricate undertaking, yet those who could successfully navigate this balance stand to reap immense rewards and remarkable success.

In addition, as explained by Janota (2021), digital assurance always prioritized the user, resulting in concrete and long-term enhancements to core experiences. To ensure the quality, security, and compliance of digital goods and services, digital assurance

adopted a broader perspective than quality assurance. Beyond simple software testing, it considered the impact of any change on the ecosystem as a whole.

As mentioned in the Wipro (2023) report, the Vice President and Global Head of Testing Services at Wipro Technologies, Kumudha Sridharan, said that digital assurance was meant to give customers a seamless and pertinent experience while safeguarding their financial and other data from hackers. She also added that businesses were prepared to make the required investments in digital assurance but the hurdle lay in fulfilling their expectations of performance guarantees.

Table 3 **Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Digital Transformation Effectiveness and the Level of Customer Experience in SSS Digital Services**

There was a significant relationship between digital transformation effectiveness and the level of customer experience in SSS digital services since the r values were .636 to .863 and interpreted with moderate positive to high positive correlation to correlate Digital Transformation Effectiveness and Customer Experience. The computed probability values of .000 were lesser than the level of significance ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

This means that the higher the level of digital transformation effectiveness, the more pleasant the customer experience becomes. By leveraging digital transformation, the agency can create meaningful and positive interactions with customers, resulting in higher customer satisfaction.

In support of the statement above, RTG Solutions Group (2023) believed that digital transformation and customer experience had become vital success factors in several businesses, including banking, healthcare, and e-commerce. Additionally, through the adoption of cutting-edge technologies and inventive approaches, companies may provide customized, effective, and user-friendly services that meet the changing demands of their clientele.

Moreover, the study of Masoud and Basahel (2023) demonstrated that digital transformation had a major beneficial impact on the customer experience, suggesting that effective implementation of these changes improved the customer experience.

Additionally, Elev8tek (2024) also mentioned that digital transformation was becoming increasingly important to provide a customized client experience as customer expectations changed

Table 4 **Proposed Action Plan**

The findings of the study show favorable results which means that the agency's digital transformation was already highly effective, however, an action plan was proposed

for areas that got the lowest mean on digital transformation and customer experience. This action plan served as a guide to enhance the current performance of the agency's technology and to maintain the confidence of the customers in the reliability of its digital services.

Conclusions

Based on the aforementioned findings of the study, the following conclusions have been derived.

1. That the agency keeps enhancing its digital goods and services, streamlining processes, and increasing efficiency in transactions by utilizing technology advancements, understanding consumer needs, and aligning them with the company's objective of providing a superior customer experience.
2. That SSS's digital services have improved its clients' overall customer experiences by including features like current data, aesthetically pleasing and easy platforms, accessibility, reliable performance, customized options, and an innovative digital profile. Additionally, the agency combines empathy into the planning and execution of digital services, catering to each client's unique requirements and preferences while achieving personalized interactions and prompt customer service, prompt and efficient responses to queries or concerns, all of which increase user engagement and improve the overall customer experience. Moreover, it demonstrates that clients have voiced their confidence in the security and privacy of their data as well as their strong preference for the agency to continuously supply accurate information and functionality, availability, and accessibility with the least amount of disruption or technical concerns possible from its digital services.
3. That the efficacy of the digital transformation increases with the level of customer experience. It follows that the agency can increase customer satisfaction by utilizing digital transformation to establish good and meaningful relationships with clients.
4. That enhancement program is necessary and beneficial to address the identified shortcomings and improve the user experience for digital services.

Recommendations

Based on the findings summarized and the conclusion obtained, the following recommendations were hereby suggested.

1. SSS may continually improve its digital offerings by simplifying the utilization of emerging technologies and providing assistance and support to clients. Additionally, increasing the speed and performance of digital systems and assuring compatibility with multiple operating systems would increase efficiency and production, resulting in higher client satisfaction. Furthermore, SSS should put proactive monitoring and event

management systems in place, as well as invest in strong infrastructure with redundancy measures, to increase dependability and improve operational efficiency. Regular testing, upkeep, and disaster recovery planning may also assist reduce downtime and guarantee that customers' access to digital services is uninterrupted.

2. SSS may continue to elevate customer experience on its digital services by prioritizing user-centric design, personalization, and accessibility. SSS may also focus on enhancing the reliability of its digital services through regular audits, redundancy measures, and proactive monitoring. Additionally, the agency may upgrade its ticketing system and add well-trained agents to streamline customer support and ensure prompt and efficient responses to user queries or complaints. Lastly, SSS may modify its existing user feedback mechanism online to actively seek evaluation or suggestions for the improvement of its digital services.

3. SSS may sustain the effectiveness of its digital transformation by continually evaluating, innovating, and adopting a customer-centric approach that will enhance positive customer experience.

4. SSS may carefully consider the proposed action plan on areas requiring improvement, incorporating it as a valuable guide for future enhancement.

5. Future researchers may contribute to expanding knowledge and understanding of how to improve digital services and customer experiences. These study subjects have the potential to stimulate innovation, improve industry practices, and eventually result in the creation of more user-centric and effective digital solutions.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adhered to a set of guidelines to maintain ethical standards at every stage of the investigation. Respondent's official consent was requested before any type of communication was initiated, ensuring that they had a clear understanding of the research purpose, procedures, and benefits. Additionally, they were informed that they could choose not to participate in the study and that any information they provided would be kept confidential and used solely for academic research purposes. The data and information that were gathered were handled with utmost care and confidentiality, following the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The research findings were reported accurately and transparently, without misinterpretation or manipulation of data.

Acknowledgments

The completion of this research paper would not have been possible without the support and contributions of numerous individuals and entities. The researcher would like to express her deepest gratitude and appreciation to the following:

She offers her deepest gratitude and thanksgiving to **Almighty God**, for being the ultimate source of wisdom and strength. She recognizes and acknowledges His divine guidance, blessings, and grace throughout this research endeavor;

Her **family**, for their unwavering support, and encouragement: to her husband, **Jhun**, for his love, understanding, and hard work in managing the household while she was occupied with her studies; to her children, **Crizza, Ron, and Nathan**, for the warm love and inspiration. They have been a constant source of motivation throughout her scholarly pursuit;

Esteemed panelists for generously sharing their expertise and providing valuable feedback during the review process. **Dr. Diosmar O. Fernandez**, Chairman of the panel, **Dr. Ma. Lorena M. Tagala**, Research Director, and **Mr. Alfredo G. Perez Jr, PhD (CAR)**, Dean of Graduate Studies, for offering insightful suggestions, constructive criticism, and meticulous attention to detail, significantly enrich the quality of this research;

Her adviser, **Ms. Marcelina DL. Perez, DBA (CAR)**, for her profound knowledge and support. Her expertise and mentorship have played a pivotal role in refining the direction and quality of this study;

The statistician, **Dr. Melchor A. Villapando**, for his steadfast response to the data analysis and study interpretation;

Mr. Daniel Angelo A. Besa, the MBA Program Chair, and one of her validators, for his meticulous review and insightful comments. Throughout her academic path, he has consistently fostered a supportive and enriching learning environment;

The **Faculty of the School of Graduate Studies**, for their knowledge, wisdom, and dedication which played a vital role in shaping her understanding and nurturing her intellectual growth;

Engr. Edwin S. Igharas, concurrent SSS Calamba Branch Head and Vice President for Luzon South I Division, and Section Head, **Ms. Carmela M. Cuento**, for their immense support and flexibility in accommodating the demands of this research project. They shared their expertise and knowledge as validators, and their guidance and trust in her abilities have truly aided her research effort;

Her **colleagues** for their collaboration and stimulating discussions, especially those who extended their hand during the survey process. Her genuine thanks go to each of them;

Lastly, everyone who has supported her in any manner, especially her new MBA buddies, **Breech, Renz**, and **Ms. Jane**, for helping and encouraging each other as they worked together to complete their research papers. Their contributions, whether big or small, have made a difference, and she is truly grateful.

REFERENCES

- Access Partnership, (2023). The growing digital economy in the Philippines.
[https://accesspartnership.com/growing-digitaleconomyphilippines/#:~:text=There%20is%20a%20significant%20economic,3%20billion\)%20in%20economic%20value](https://accesspartnership.com/growing-digitaleconomyphilippines/#:~:text=There%20is%20a%20significant%20economic,3%20billion)%20in%20economic%20value)
- Albukhitan, S. (2020). Developing digital transformation strategy for manufacturing. *Procedia computer science*, 170, 664-671.
- Alvarenga A, Matos F, Godina R, C. O. Matias J. (2020). Digital Transformation and Knowledge Management in the Public Sector. *Sustainability*, 12(14):5824.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su12145824>

- Awadhi, J., Obeidat, B., & Alshurideh, M. (2021). The impact of customer service digitalization on customer satisfaction: Evidence from telecommunication industry. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 5(4), 815-830.
- Bascur, C. & Rusu, C. (2020). Customer Experience in Retail: A Systematic Literature Review. *Applied Sciences*, 10(21), 7644. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10217644>
- Becker, L. & Jaakkola, E. (2020). Customer experience: fundamental premises and implications for research. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 48, 630-648.
- Borges, G. L., Marine, P., & Ibrahim, D. Y. (2020). Digital transformation and customer services: the banking revolution. *International Journal of Open Information Technologies*, 8(7), 124-128.
- Brunetti, F., Matt, D. T., Bonfanti, A., De Longhi, A., Pedrini, G., & Orzes, G. (2020). Digital transformation challenges: strategies emerging from a multi-stakeholder approach. *The TQM Journal*, 32(4), 697-724.
- Butt, A., Imran, F., Helo, P., & Kantola, J. (2024). Strategic design of culture for digital transformation. *Long Range Planning*, 57(2), 102415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2024.102415>
- Carlos, RA (2023). DBM launch digital transformation Roadmap. Philippine News Agency. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1206496>
- Chen, J.-S., Le, T.-T. and Florence, D. (2021), "Usability and responsiveness of artificial intelligence chatbot on online customer experience in e-retailing", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 49 No. 11, pp. 1512-1531. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJRDM-08-2020-0312>
- Clapano, J. (2023, June 4). DICT: 83% of Pinoys are internet users, but...Philstar Global <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2023/06/04/2271289/dict-83-pinoys-are-internet-users-but>
- Collins, G. (2023). Impact of Digitalization on Customer Experience Management in the Hospitality Industry. *Hospitality and Tourism Journal*, 1(1), 12-23.
- Correani, A., De Massis, A., Frattini, F., Petruzzelli, A. M., & Natalicchio, A. (2020). Implementing a digital strategy: Learning from the experience of three digital transformation projects. *California Management Review*, 62(4), 37-56.
- Deep, G. (2023). Digital transformation's impact on organizational culture. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*. 10. 396-401. [10.30574/ijrsra.2023.10.2.0977](https://doi.org/10.30574/ijrsra.2023.10.2.0977). <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijrsra.2023.10.2.0977>
- Exito Media Concepts Pvt Ltd (2022, December 14). Key Factors Driving Digital Transformation in the Philippines. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/key-factors-driving-digital-transformation-philippines-/>
- Elev8tek (2024). How Digital Transformation is Driving Customer Experience. <https://www.elev8me.com/insights/how-digital-transformation-drives-customer-experience>
- Gokalp, E., & Martinez, V. (2021). Digital transformation capability maturity model enabling the assessment of industrial manufacturers. *Computers in Industry*, 132, 103522.

- Gupta, V. (2024). Impact of Consumer Digital Experience on Consumer Reliability in the Context of Indian Banking Sector, PREPRINT (Version 1)
<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4138668/v1>
- Hadid, K. I., Omar, S. S., & Soon, N. K. (2022). The mediating effect of customer satisfaction on the relationship between digital banking service quality and customer loyalty. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(8), 8582-8599.
- Hanelt, A., Bohnsack, R., Marz, D., & Antunes Marante, C. (2021). A systematic review of the literature on digital transformation: Insights and implications for strategy and organizational change. *Journal of Management Studies*, 58(5), 1159-1197.
- Heller, J., Chylinski, M., de Ruyter, K., Keeling, D. I., Hilken, T., & Mahr, D. (2021). Tangible Service Automation: Decomposing the Technology-Enabled Engagement Process (TEEP) for Augmented Reality. *Journal of Service Research*, 24(1), 84-103.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1094670520933692>
- Hoque, U.S., Akhter, N., Absar, N., Khandaker, MU. ., & Al-Mamun, A. (2023). Assessing Service Quality Using SERVQUAL Model: An Empirical Study on Some Private Universities in Bangladesh. *Trends in Higher Education*. 2(1):255-269. <https://doi.org/10.3390/higheredu2010013>
- Ivančić, L., Vukšić, V. B., & Spremić, M. (2019). Mastering the digital transformation process: Business practices and lessons learned. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 9(2).
- Janota, D. (2024, January 31). Why Digital Assurance and Digital Transformation Go Hand-in-hand.
<https://www.ciklum.com/resources/blog/why-digital-assurance-and-digital-transformation-go-hand-in-hand#:~:text=Digital%20assurance%20is%20a%20type,far%20beyond%20simple%20software%20testing>.
- Jaumotte, F., Oikonomou, M., Pizzinelli C., Tavares, M. M.(2023, March 21). How Pandemic Accelerated Digital Transformation in Advances Economies. IMF Blog.
<https://www.imf.org/en/Blogs/Articles/2023/03/21/how-pandemic-accelerated-digital-transformation-in-advanced-economies>
- Kemp, S. (2023, February 9). Digital 2023: The Philippines. Datareportal.
<https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2023-philippines>
- Khan, A. (2023, May 25). The Power of Empathy: Building Connections in the Digital World. Modern Diplomacy.
<https://moderndiplomacy.eu/2023/05/25/the-power-of-empathy-building-connections-in-the-digital-world/>
- Khatoun, S., Zhengliang, X., & Hussain, H. (2020). The Mediating Effect of customer satisfaction on the relationship between Electronic banking service quality and customer Purchase intention: Evidence from the Qatar banking sector. *Sage Open*, 10(2), 2158244020935887.
- Korach, M. (2023, July 16). Customer Responsiveness. Dealhub.
<https://dealhub.io/glossary/customer-responsiveness/>
- Kraus, S., Jones, P., Kailer, N., Weinmann, A., Chaparro-Banegas, N., & Roig-Tierno, N. (2021). Digital transformation: An overview of the current state of the art of research. *Sage Open*, 11(3), 21582440211047576.

- Lund, J. (2023, March 9). How customer experience drives digital transformation. SuperOffice.
<https://www.superoffice.com/blog/digital-transformation/>
- Masoud, R. & Basahel, S. (2023). The effects of digital transformation on firm performance: The role of customer experience and IT innovation. *Digital*, 3(2), 109-126.
- Mathis, S. (2021, January 29). Empathy in Customer Experience Drives Company Success. Techtarget.
<https://www.techtarget.com/searchcustomerexperience/tip/Empathy-in-customer-experience-drives-company-success>
- Mckinsey & Company (2022). What is CX.
<https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/mckinsey-explainers/what-is-cx>
- Mergel, I., Edelman, N., & Haug, N. (2019). Defining digital transformation: Results from expert interviews. *Government Information Quarterly*, 36(4), 101385.
- Mikalef, P. & Parmiggiani, E. (2022). An Introduction to Digital Transformation. In: Mikalef, P., Parmiggiani, E. (eds) *Digital Transformation in Norwegian Enterprises*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-05276-7_1
- Mishra, D. B., Haider, I., Gunasekaran, A., Sakib, M. N., Malik, N., & Rana, N. P. (2023). "Better together": Right blend of business strategy and digital transformation strategies. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 266, 109040.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0925527323002724?via%3Dihub>
- Mohsen, M. & Magdi, D. (2022). Exploring the impact of the relationship between the digital transformation and the performance efficiency at governmental sector. *المحاسبة والحاسبات وتكنولوجيا المعلومات لنظم المصرية الجمعية مجلة*, 28(28), 24-33.
- Moore, J. (2023, October 20). How digital transformation is changing customer experience. Tech Target.
<https://www.techtarget.com/searchcio/tip/How-digital-transformation-is-changingcustomerexperience#:~:text=Digital%20transformation%20and%20customer%20experience,easier%20ways%20to%20query%20data.&text=When%20organizations%20talk%20digital%20transformation,the%20subtext%20of%20the%20conversation.>
- Nelson, K. (2023, February 23). How governments can enhance digital customer experience with technology. Opentext.
<https://blogs.opentext.com/how-governments-can-enhance-digital-customer-experience-with-technology/>
- Oracle (2023). What is customer experience(CX). <https://www.oracle.com/ph/cx/what-is-cx/>
- Pearce, G. (2020). Attaining digital transformation readiness, *ISACA Journal*, vol.1, 2020.
<https://www.isaca.org/resources/isaca-journal/issues/2020/volume-1/attaining-digital-transformation-readiness>
- Ranchordas, S. (2021). Empathy in the digital administrative state. *Duke LJ*, 71, 1341.
- Reganit, J. C. (2023). CSC urge governments to pursue digital transformation. Philippine News Agency.

- <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1204848#:~:text=MANILA%20%E2%80%93%20The%20Civil%20Service%20Commission,service%20in%20times%20of%20crisis.>
- Roy, S. K., Gruner, R. L., & Guo, J. (2022). Exploring customer experience, commitment, and engagement behaviours. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 30(1), 45-68
- RTG Solutions Group, Inc. (2023). Impact of digital transformation and customer experience. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/impact-digital-transformation-customer-experience/>
- Sharma, L. R., Jha, S., Koirala, R., Aryal, U., & Bhattarai, T. (2023). Navigating the research landscape: A guide to the selection of the right research design. *International Research Journal of MMC (IRJMMC)*, 4(1), 64-78.
- Social Security System. (August 2023). Facts and Figures. [Pamphlet].
- Susanto, S. A., Manek, M. V., Setiawan, R. A., & Mustikasari, F. (2023). Customer experience in digital banking: The convenience, security, and usefulness on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in Indonesia. *Devotion: Journal of Research and Community Service*, 4(8), 1671-1685.
- TAFF, Inc. (2021, September 9). How Digital Transformation Drives Tangible Customer Experience. <https://www.taffinc.com/blog/how-digital-transformation-drives-tangible-customer-experience/>
- Tekic, Z. & Koroteev, D. (2019). From disruptively digital to proudly analog: A holistic typology of digital transformation strategies. *Business Horizons*, 62(6), 683-693.
- Tian, M., Chen, Y., Tian, G., Huang, W., & Hu, C. (2023). The role of digital transformation practices in the operations improvement in manufacturing firms: a practice-based view. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 262, 108929.
- Udovita, P. V. M. V. D. (2020). Conceptual review on dimensions of digital transformation in the modern era. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 10(2), 520-529.
- Van Veldhoven, Z. & Vanthienen, J. (2022). Digital transformation is an interaction-driven perspective between business, society, and technology. *Electronic Markets*, 32(2), 629-644.
- VELOSIO (2023, January 13). Digital Transformation Maturity Model. <https://www.velosio.com/blog/digital-transformation-maturity-model/>
- Verhoef, P. C., Broekhuizen, T., Bart, Y., Bhattacharya, A., Dong, J. Q., Fabian, N., & Haenlein, M. (2021). Digital transformation: A multidisciplinary reflection and research agenda. *Journal of business research*, 122, 889-901.
- Waqas, M., Hamzah, Z.L.B., & Salleh, N.A.M. (2021) Customer experience: a systematic literature review and consumer culture theory-based conceptualization. *Manag Rev Q* 71, 135–176 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-020-00182-w>
- Watts, S. (2020, July 8). Digital Platforms,: A Brief Introduction. <https://www.bmc.com/blogs/digital-platforms/>
- Wipro (2023, October). Digital Assurance: Reaching a Seamless Customer Experience

<https://www.wipro.com/cloud/digital-assurance-reaching-a-seamless-customer-experience/>

Xiao, J., Han, L., & Zhang, H. (2022). Exploring Driving Factors of Digital Transformation among Local Governments: Foundations for Smart City Construction in China. *Sustainability*, 14(22):14980.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su142214980>

Yu, J., Wang, J., & Moon, T. (2022). Influence of digital transformation capability on operational performance. *Sustainability*, 14(13), 7909.

Zaoui, F. & Souissi, N. (2020). Roadmap for digital transformation: A literature review. *Procedia Computer Science*, 175, 621-628.
<https://www.questionpro.com/blog/servqual/#:~:text=The%20Servqual%20model%20is%20based,how%20good%20the%20service%20is>
